

Examination of the Reasons for Poor interest by Graduates of Building in Professional Registration in Anambra State.

Micheal Chiedozie Alozie_Dike¹, Oluwatayomi Daniel Fadumo¹, Aluka Chinedu Franklin¹, Charles Adewunmi Adedoja² and Adesina Musbau Adebola¹

Affiliations

1. Department of Building, Faculty of Environmental Sciences, Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka -Anambra State.
2. Department of Building, Faculty of Environmental Sciences, Southern Delta University Ozoro, Delta State.

Corresponding Author

od.fadumo@unizik.edu.ng

ARTICLE INFO

©2025 RS Publication

Paper ID: IJRES-69246E660BFA4

Received: 2025-10-27

Published: 2025-11-27

DOI:

<https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17733200>

Page No: 136-140

RS PUBLICATION
PIONEERS OF SCIENCE, UNLOCKED

ABSTRACT

In Nigeria, building graduates are required to register with NIOB to gain formal recognition as professional builders. This registration grants them access to career growth, professional networking, and legal authorization to practice as certified builders. The declining rate of professional registration among building graduates poses a significant threat to the construction industry in Nigeria.; without professional registration, many practitioners lack the required training and accountability, leading to substandard practices, ethical violations, and diminished public trust. This study aims to examine the reasons for poor interest of graduates of building in professional registration in Anambra State, Nigeria, with a view to recommend strategies for increased participation. This study employed descriptive survey research design, which is appropriate for examine the poor interest of building graduates in professional registration in Anambra state. The findings indicate general agreement that some factors are significant barriers to professional registration. This suggests that respondents recognizes the challenges impacting their interest in registration, with varying degrees of intensity. The item "Financial constraints" had the highest mean (4.09), reflecting significant agreement among respondents that cost related barriers are a major deterrent. Conversely, the item "Perceived irrelevance of registration" had the lowest mean (3.76), indicating it is a notable but relatively less severe barrier compared to financial and procedural issues. The range of mean scores (3.76 to 4.09) implies that responses were relatively consistent, highlighting the prominence of these factors among building graduates in Anambra State. Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that policymakers introduce graduatefriendly reforms, such as reducing registration fees, offering financial incentives like tax breaks, and linking registration to career advancement opportunities, including eligibility for senior roles or government contracts. These measures are intended to alleviate financial barriers and motivate graduates to pursue professional certification.

Key words: Building Graduates, Professional registration, Construction Professionals, Building, Construction certification

Cite This Paper: Micheal Chiedozie Alozie_Dike, Oluwatayomi Daniel Fadumo, Aluka Chinedu Franklin, Charles Adewunmi Adedoja and Adesina Musbau Adebola (2025). "Examination of the Reasons for Poor interest by Graduates of Building in Professional Registration in Anambra State.". *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ADVANCED SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNICAL RESEARCH (IJASTR)*, vol. 15, no. 6, 2025, pp. 136-140. DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17733200>

1.0 Introduction

A graduate is an individual who has completed a course of study at a university or higher institution and has been awarded a degree in a specific field (Aghimien, Aigbavboa, Oke and Aliu, 2023). For this study, a graduate refers specifically to individuals who have obtained a degree in Building from a recognized Nigerian university or polytechnic. These graduates are expected to transition into professional practice, where they contribute to the construction industry through planning, supervision, and project execution. Professional registration is the official process by which graduates in a specific field meet the requirements set by a professional body to become licensed or certified practitioners (Oladimeji and Yusuf, 2021). In Nigeria, building graduates are required to register with NIOB to gain formal recognition as professional builders. This registration grants them access to career growth, professional networking, and legal authorization to practice as certified builders. Despite these advantages, many building graduates have a poor interest in professional registration (Oladimeji and Yusuf, 2021). NIOB, established in 1967, plays a key role in regulating the building profession in Nigeria (NIOB, 2022). It provides a structured pathway for graduates to become certified professionals, offering designations such as Graduate Membership, Associate Membership, and Corporate Membership. However, studies indicate that several challenges discourage graduates from pursuing this registration. The declining rate of professional registration among building graduates poses a significant threat to the construction industry in Nigeria. Without professional registration, many practitioners lack the required training and accountability, leading to substandard practices, ethical violations, and diminished public trust (Oyewobi, Windapo and Rotimi, 2017). This study aims to examine the reasons for poor interest of graduates of building in professional registration in Anambra State, Nigeria, with a view to recommend strategies for increased participation. This study is important to the building profession in Nigeria, particularly in addressing the persistent issue of poor interest in professional registration among building graduates.

2.0 Literature Review

2.1 Reason for Poor Interest by Building graduates in Professional Registration

Various studies have highlighted several barriers that hinder building graduates from pursuing Professional Registration:

1. **Lack of Awareness:** Many building graduates are not fully informed about the benefits and procedures of professional registration. Studies indicate that inadequate orientation during undergraduate studies contributes to this gap in knowledge (Opawole and Jagboro, 2016). Similarly, Okafor (2018) found that many graduates remain unaware of how registration can enhance career prospects.
2. **Financial Constraints:** The costs associated with professional registration, including examination and membership fees, can create a significant financial burden. Research conducted by Adebayo and Chukwu (2020), and further supported by Okafor (2018), indicates that graduates, who often prioritize immediate employment, struggle to justify the expenses related to registration.
3. **Perceived Irrelevance of Registration:** A common theme in the literature is that many graduates perceive professional registration as less important due to its limited enforcement in the job market. This perspective is supported by Oladimeji and Yusuf (2021), who observes that many graduates prioritize practical experience over certification.

4. Bureaucratic and Cumbersome Processes: The registration process is often seen as complex and bureaucratic, discouraging graduates from initiating the procedure. Both Oladimeji and Yusuf (2021) and Opawole and Jagboro, (2016) have highlighted the need for streamlining these processes to make registration more accessible.

2.2 Implications of Poor Interests by Building Graduates in Professional Registration.

The poor interest of building graduates to pursue professional registration has significant repercussions on Nigeria's construction industry. Empirical studies from the past decade highlight several critical implications:

1. **Unregulated Practices:** The poor interest of professional registration is associated with unethical practices, such as the use of substandard materials and compromised safety protocols. These lapses can have serious consequences for both builders and the public. A study by (Oyewobi, Windapo and Rotimi, 2017) highlighted that unethical professional practices adversely affect the performance of construction projects in Nigeria.
2. **Increased Incidence of Building Failures:** The poor interest of registered professionals may lead to inadequately supervised construction projects, which in turn can result in building collapses and structural failures (Oyewobi, Windapo and Rotimi, 2017). This issue is further emphasized in studies by Okafor (2018).
3. **Emergence of Unqualified Practitioners:** A shortage of professionally registered builders creates opportunities for unqualified individuals to operate within the industry. This influx often leads to substandard work, increased rework, and various quality issues. Obaju and Musa (2022) notes that the insufficient number of registered professionals allows quacks to thrive, resulting in building failures and compromised construction quality.
4. **Diminished Professional Standards:** Professional bodies play a crucial role in upholding standards and ethics within the construction industry. A decline in professional registration undermines these standards, leading to subpar practices. The Builders Act emphasizes the importance of registering qualified builders to maintain industry standards (Oyewobi, Windapo and Rotimi, 2017)
5. **Limited Career Advancement:** Without professional registration, career progression opportunities are often limited. Registered professionals typically have access to a broader network, continuous professional development, and leadership roles. The Nigerian Institute of Building (NIOB) highlights that a small population of registered professionals can be a disadvantage, limiting career growth and industry influence. (Nigerian Institute of Building, 2022)
6. **Economic Implications:** The under-utilization of skilled graduates due to a lack of professional registration can negatively impact the economy. Unemployed or underemployed graduates contribute less to economic growth and may increase the dependency ratio. Eneji, Mai-Lafia and Weiping (2013) discuss how graduate unemployment poses socio-economic challenges, necessitating deliberate policies to address the issue.

In summary, key barriers to professional registration include limited awareness, financial constraints, and bureaucratic challenges. Studies indicate that many graduates receive inadequate orientation on professional registration during their undergraduate studies (Opawole and Jagboro, 2016). High registration and examination fees further discourage graduates, as they prioritize securing employment

over certification (Adebayo and Chukwu, 2020; Okafor, 2018). Additionally, the cumbersome registration process creates further obstacles (Oladimeji and Yusuf, 2021).

3.0 Methodology

This study employed descriptive survey research design, which is appropriate for examine the poor interest of building graduates in professional registration in Anambra state. This study focuses on Anambra State, Nigeria . One of the leading states in the southeastern region, known for its educational institutions, commercial activities, and expanding construction sector (National Universities Commission, 2023). The population of this study comprises graduates of Building from higher institutions in Anambra State within the past five years. However, the last two years were not considered, as graduates are required to undergo a tutelage period before being eligible to seek professional certification. The study, therefore, focuses on graduates who completed their undergraduate studies from 2020-2022 but have not yet obtained professional certification. Specifically, this includes graduates from Nnamdi Azikiwe University, UNIZIK (90), and Federal Polytechnic, Oko (126). Data collected through the use of Google Forms was analyzed using descriptive statistical methods. In this study, the researcher focused on using frequency distributions, percentages, and mean scores to identify trends and patterns related to professional registration among building graduates.

4.0 Findings

Out of the 216 questionnaires distributed, 204 were returned, achieving a response rate of 94.4%.

STATEMENTS	SA	A	N	D	SD	Mean	Ranking
Lack of awareness	70	60	40	24	10	3.79	3rd
Financial constraints	90	65	30	15	4	4.09	1st
Perceived irrelevance of registration	60	70	50	20	4	3.76	4th
Bureaucratic and cumbersome processes	85	60	35	20	4	4.00	2nd
Average						3.91	

Source: Research’s fields Survey, 2025

From Table 4.1, it can be observed that the mean scores for all responses were above the midpoint of 3.91, indicating general agreement that these factors are significant barriers to professional registration. This suggests that respondents recognize the challenges impacting their interest in registration, with varying degrees of intensity. The item “Financial constraints” had the highest mean (4.09), reflecting significant agreement among respondents that cost-related barriers are a major deterrent. Conversely, the item “Perceived irrelevance of registration” had the lowest mean (3.76), indicating it is a notable but relatively less severe barrier compared to financial and procedural issues. The range of mean scores (3.76 to 4.09) implies that responses were relatively consistent, highlighting the prominence of these factors among building graduates in Anambra State. In summary, The findings in Table 4.1 agrees with previous study by Oyewobi, Windapo and Rotimi(2017).

5.0 Conclusion

The main reason for low interest in professional registration in Anambra state is primarily due to the financial costs and the lengthy/bureaucratic procedures needed for professional registration.

6.0 Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that policymakers introduce graduate-friendly reforms, such as reducing registration fees, offering financial incentives like tax breaks, and linking registration to career advancement opportunities, including eligibility for senior roles or government contracts. These measures are intended to alleviate financial barriers and motivate graduates to pursue professional certification.

7.0 References

- Adebayo, K., and Chukwu, T. (2020). Challenges in professional registration among building graduates in Nigeria. *Journal of Construction Management*, 15(3), 112–125
- Aghimien, D. O., Aigbavboa, C. O., and Oke, A. E. (2018). Enhancing competencies of architecture graduates through industry-academia collaboration.
- Eneji, M. A., Mai-Lafia, D., & Weiping, S. (2013). Socio-economic impact of graduate unemployment on Nigeria and the vision 20:2020. *International Journal of Development and Sustainability*, 2(1), 148-161.
- Nigerian Environmental Management Journal. (2022). Environmental impacts of urbanization in Anambra State.
- National Universities Commission. (2023). Directory of accredited programs in Nigerian tertiary institutions
- Obaju, B., Musa, S., & Abass, J. O. (2022). Registration challenges of built environment professions into professional institutions. *International Journal of Built Environment and Sustainability*, 9(2-3), 11-20
- Okafor, E. (2018). Assessing the challenges of professional registration among construction graduates in Nigeria. *International Journal of Construction Education*, 12(3), 250–265.
- Oladimeji, J., and Yusuf, A. (2021). Barriers to professional registration in Nigeria's building sector: A case study of NIOB. *International Journal of Built Environment Studies*, 8(2), 57–68.
- Opawole, A., and Jagboro, G. O. (2016). Factors influencing professional registration among construction professionals in Nigeria. *International Journal of Construction Management*, 16(3), 215-226.
- Oyewobi, Windapo and Rotimi, L. O., Windapo, A. O., and Rotimi, J. O. B. (2017). Unethical professional practices and performance of construction projects in Nigeria, 4(4), 175-182.